

Srinagar City Road Accident and Safety Analysis

Danish Parmu

M. Tech Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, RIMT University, Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab, India

Correspondence should be addressed to Dansih Parmu; hunk.dp@gmail.com.

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ABSTRACT- Road accidents, which kill countless people worldwide, are one of the greatest man-made disasters we face today in the world of current revenue sources. Road accidents are still a significant barrier to sustainable human progress, particularly in developing nations. After extensive research in this area, practical experience has shown that such annihilation can be reduced to a minimum to some extent, and industrialised nations have so offered several safety precautions. Road accidents are still a major issue, or one could even say a threat to India's ability to advance economically and socially. Every year, more than 1 lakh persons in India are killed in traffic accidents and many more suffer injuries. In the last five years, there have been more than 8000 road accidents in Srinagar, the capital of Jammu and Kashmir during the summer. Therefore, it is imperative to adopt a mandatory action to improve the city's climate for road safety. Therefore, it is imperative that all relevant institutions, including those related to government, law enforcement, and other institutional mechanisms, come together for this purpose in order to reach a better decision that will either end accidents altogether or at the very least reduce their frequency to the absolute minimum.

KEYWORDS- Safety Analysis, Srinagar City, and Road Accidents

I. INTRODUCTION

Road networks are important to a nation's social and economic policy. The transportation sector is a crucial component of practically every aspect of daily life. In the current world situation, road accidents are a serious problem. Traffic congestion-related incidents on the road are the 10th most common cause of death and injury worldwide. Considering a few WHO statistics on traffic accidents:

- Up to 1.2 million people every year perish in traffic accidents[1].
- Each year, nearly 50 million people are injured or rendered incapacitated in traffic accidents.
- According to studies, more than half of the victims are at-risk drivers.
- Up to 4% of a country's GNP is lost due to traffic accidents[6].
- Correct seat belt use lowers accident fatality risk by 61% [2]
- Up to 45% less people who wear helmets suffer fatal and serious head injuries. Road accidents are rising alarmingly quickly in developing nations and, in some cases, have surpassed diseases that formerly afflicted the organisations to improve roads. By personally visiting

populace in severity. When South Asian nations are taken into account, almost 428,000 persons per year pass away in traffic accidents. Road fatalities top the list of unintentional deaths in India by a significant margin over incidents like drowning, fire, air or rail catastrophes etc. According to annual data, the Indian roads are essentially turning into death traps, with about 90,000 fatalities per kilometer is .028. The general public's lack of awareness of road safety, the indifference of policymakers and implementers, and other factors all combine to affect it. According to WHO predictions, the number of fatalities and injuries from traffic accidents would rise from ninth to third on the list of the most pressing health issues by 2022. [12]

II. MATERIALS

A. Study area and data collection

A study subject and information gathering. traffic flow characteristics are a collection of interconnected complicated components. complete study must take into account such as time headway, volume, density, delay, speed, etc .therefore conventional data collection methods fall short of meeting these requirements. Accurate measurements of vehicle headways and speed on road networks are necessary for congestion modeling. It is crucial to measure vehicle flow, vehicle speed, time headway and vehicle makeup are all necessary pieces of information[9].

III. HASSLE

India's situation is pretty alarming. According to a report by the Ministry of Road Transportation and Highway,[MORTH] there were 4,86,477 road accidents overall, 1,37,570 people were killed, and 8,95,000 people were injured (in 2019). Since traffic accidents in Srinagar have reached an alarming high, it is important to find them, thoroughly investigate them, and conduct a safety study. [7]

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Information gathered from secondary sources: From the relevant government departments, statistics relating to different types of traffic accidents, their causes, vehicles involved, and the age range of the victims throughout India and Srinagar city have been acquired actions conducted by law enforcement agencies, such as the application of sanctions and legal action. The action made by government

various divisions, we were able to attain safety. Information

gathered through semi-structured interviews: Srinagar city's law enforcement and road safety personnel were questioned about their opinions on accidents, the state of road safety, and the challenges they have had to overcome in improvising.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

As per, Mr. Abid Hussain, Regional Transportation Officer's information The Motor Vehicle Department has registered 785,636 automobiles. He also stated that over 1.7 lakh vehicles have been added to J&K's Vehicle population annually during the past three years. Thus, these figures point to a tremendous increase in Srinagar's population of road transport. There are just 800 signal men in whole of J&K, according to sources, while thousands are needed [Kashmir News Service]. In the city of Srinagar, there is low overall road safety. The information in the table above reveals a lot about the number of accidents, injuries, and fatalities in the year in question. Although the fatality rate per 100,000 vehicles is lower than that of other large Indian cities, there is nevertheless cause for concern because Srinagar has less traffic than other wealthy nations. According to official statistics, Srinagar City adds 90,000 new vehicles each year to its vehicle population. The primary cause of traffic congestion and accident-causing factors is the growth in road traffic and the narrowness of the roads. The yellow marking on the Residency Road side of the street appears to designate parking spaces for patrons.

VI. CONCLUSION

The primary issue is in both the government and the public, according to a thorough analysis of Srinagar City's traffic flow and road situation. Massive road accidents and fatalities on Srinagar city's roads are caused by a lack of enforcement of traffic laws and regulations, a lack of public knowledge and education regarding road use, and some flaws in road design. Although there are authorities in place to ensure road safety in cities, study reveals that their fundamental weakness is a lack of coordination, which has an impact on the upkeep of roads. Even if accountable decision-makers are present in several institutions, there is little to no operational coordination between them. Road safety is a broad topic, so it needs to be approached from all angles. The success of this programme indirectly depends on the combination of the efforts of the major stakeholders in this field. However, integrated policy-making cannot be successful if the decision-makers, who are dispersed across several institutions, do not work well together. The Netherlands and Sweden's experience with best practices in road safety show how authorities can work together and be held accountable for quick outcomes. In the case of Srinagar as well as throughout India, the execution of policies in all disciplines as well as agency coordination continue to be the main areas of concern. This essay illustrates how national interest affects how well a road safety strategy works. The road transportation division is concerned with a number of issues, including the control of motor vehicle movement, the issuance of driving licences, pollution check drives, fitness and safety concerns, and the building and maintenance of all major and nearby roads. Practices in the Netherlands and Sweden show how important policy choices are made by establishing

objectives and carrying out programmes while coordinating efforts from numerous agencies to successfully meet objectives. Setting goals helps to define strategies, assign tasks to responsible leaders and program-related agencies, and ensure that the right actions are taken to achieve the goal. Setting goals demonstrates the government's commitment to lowering the number of fatalities on the road and its ability to maintain proposed policy and legislative reforms as well as allocate sufficient funds to undertake safety campaigns.

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